

Designing a 3D model of a one-story ecological house

3D design of an energy-efficient ecological house includes the process of developing and creating a construction project aimed at creating housing that uses energy efficiently and minimizes the negative impact on the environment. Design-research of an eco-house is an important stage in the creation of ecologically clean and sustainable housing. It allows you to show which specific ecological and energy-efficient solutions will be most effective for the house and helps to identify the optimal solutions and develop the concept of an ecological house, taking into account energy efficiency, environmental friendliness and the health of the residents.

Sketch design of an eco-house helps you determine the main aspects of the house and develop a concept that meets the principles of sustainability and sustainability. Based on the received information and sketches, a layout of the design object is created. At this stage, the features of the house planning should be worked out - the plan of the premises and their functional location, the visualization of the appearance of the house taking into account the architectural style and the use of ecological materials, showing the use of ecological materials and structures, indicating the insulation materials and insulation system, and showing the elements of landscape design.

Creating a 3D building model in Fusion 360 covers:

1. Building planning, includes dimensions, materials, functional requirements and the purpose of modeling.
2. Using special 3D software, walls, roofs, windows, doors and other basic elements are created. This geometry serves as the basis for further detailing of the model.
3. Adding details and textures.
4. Lighting and visualization: At this stage, lighting sources are installed in the building and visualization is carried out, which allows you to see the building from different angles and lighting.

5. The final stage of the simulation is a check from the point of view of energy efficiency, ergonomics, structural strength, which is carried out during the simulation and to identify possible problems or improve the design.

To create a 3D model of an ecological house, it is suggested to use the Autodesk Fusion 360 software. During construction, it is necessary to create a rectangle and duplicate it the required number of times using the "Rectangular Pattern" command, taking into account the gaps between the future bricks.

With the help of the "Extrude" command, we add the necessary width to the first row of soil blocks and create a second row in a checkerboard sequence and move "Move/Copy" to the distance of the width of the bricks of the first row and the gap for concrete.

We duplicate two rows of soil blocks with the "Rectangular Pattern" command as many times as necessary to obtain the height of the building. We use the "Appearance" command to create the texture of the soil blocks and set the characteristics.

When the soil blocks are built, create an imitation of a concrete solution by sketching a rectangle in the shape of the building, extruding with the "Extrude" command, cutting to the shape of the brick with "Combine". Figure 1 shows the characteristics of the concrete solution without taking into account the weight of the bricks.

Figure 1 – Characteristics of concrete

Figure 2 shows how the 3D model looks after creating walls and partitions between rooms using the Extrude and Rectangular Pattern commands, leaving a 900mm space for the door. Openings for doors and windows are made using "Extrude". Each detail has its own material.

Figure 2 – Design of windows and doors

To build the roof, we first create a sketch and add volume using the "Extrude" functions. The finished result of the 3D model of an ecological house is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – 3D model of an energy-efficient ecological house

The 3D model of an ecological house is shown in Figure 3, the area of which is 127.57 m².